

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF PAN- AND PITCH-BASED HYBRID CARBON FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY MATRIX COMPOSITES

K. Naito^{1*}

¹ Composite Materials Group, National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS), Japan

* Corresponding author (NAITO.Kimiyoshi@nims.go.jp)

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1 Introduction

Fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites (FRP) have become a dominant material in the aerospace, automotive and sporting goods industries [1]. Some of these FRP are useful, however, only in highly specialized situations where limitations such as brittle fracture behavior are considered. By mixing two or more types of fiber in a common matrix to form a hybrid FRP it may be possible to create a material possessing the combined advantages of the individual FRP [2].

There had been a number of papers written on the advantages and applications of hybrid FRP around 1980 [2-4]. In 1972, *Hayashi et al* [4] has showed the tensile properties of carbon/glass fibers hybrid FRP and proposed a hybrid FRP design method based on the rule of mixtures. For experimental results, the fracture strength and failure strain were higher than those of carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites (CFRP). *Short et al* [5,6], *Hardaker et al* [7], *Chou et al* [8] reviewed the hybrid FRP. However, carbon/glass, carbon/aramid fibers were mainly used in previous investigation. This interest stems from a brief that a more cost-effective utilization of more expensive fiber may result if it is used in hybrid form [9].

Polyacrylonitrile (PAN)- and pitch-based carbon fibers are widely used as a reinforcement in CFRP because of their high specific strength and modulus [10-12]. The trends toward the development of carbon fibers have been driven in two directions; high strength fibers with very high tensile strength and a fairly high strain to failure (~2 %) and high modulus fiber with very high stiffness and low strain to failure. Today, a number of high strength (more than 5 GPa) PAN-based and high modulus (more than 800 GPa) pitch-based carbon fibers have been commercially available [13-15].

Recently, the tensile properties of high strength PAN-based (IM600) and high modulus pitch-based (K13D) hybrid CFRP were characterized by *Naito et al* [16]. As the results, the tensile stress-strain curve of the hybrid CFRP shows a complicated shape (jagged trace). By the high modulus pitch-based carbon fiber, the hybrid CFRP shows the high modulus in the initial stage of loading. Subsequently, when the high modulus carbon fiber begins to fail, the high strength fiber would hold the load (strength) and the material continues to endure high load without instantaneous failure. The observed stress after the initial fracture was improved by the enhancing the delamination energy.

In the present work, the tensile properties of high strength PAN-based (IM600) and high modulus pitch-based (K13D) hybrid CFRP with different hybrid ratios (IM600 CFRP layer/K13D CFRP layer) were fabricated due to control the delamination phenomena. The tensile tests of these hybrid CFRP was performed and to evaluate the potential of them.

2 Experimental procedure

2.1 Materials

CFRP laminates were produced using an epoxy matrix based unidirectional CFRP prepreg material QC133-149A (fiber: IM600, matrix: 133) and HYEJ16M95DHX1 (fiber: K13D, matrix: HX1). IM600 and K13D carbon fibers were a high strength PAN-based and a high modulus pitch-based carbon fibers, respectively. The physical and mechanical properties of IM600 PAN-based and K13D pitch-based carbon fibers are listed in Table 1 [13,15]. IM600 (QC133-149A) prepreg was supplied from Toho Tenax Co., Ltd. and K13D (HYEJ16M95DHX1) prepreg was supplied from

Mitsubishi Plastics, Inc. All sheets were manufactured using conventional prepreg technology. CFRP prepreps with a nominal thickness of 0.142 mm (QC133-149A, FAW (fiber area weight): 145 g/m², RC (resin content): 35 %) and 0.133 mm (HYEJ16M95DHX1, FAW: 160 g/m², RC: 33 %) were used.

Table 1. Physical and mechanical properties of IM600 and K13D carbon fibers.

Fiber	IM600 PAN-based	K13D pitch-based
Density ^a ρ_f (g/cm ³)	1.80	2.20
Tensile modulus ^a E_f (GPa)	285	935
Tensile strength ^a σ_f (GPa)	5.79	3.70
Failure strain ^a ε_f (%)	2.0	0.4
Tensile modulus ^b E_f (GPa)	281 ±28	940 ±48
Tensile strength ^b σ_f (GPa)	5.20 ±0.87	3.21 ±0.81
Failure strain ^b ε_f (%)	1.81 ±0.31	0.36 ±0.08

^a Producer's data sheet

IM600: Catalog for Toho Tenax Filament, Toho Tenax Co.,Ltd., Properties of Filament. 2008.

K13D: Catalog for DIALEAD, Mitsubishi Plastics, Inc., High performance coal tar pitch carbon fiber. 2009.

^b Single filament tensile data (25 mm gauge length) from previous investigation [13,15].

2.2 Specimen preparation

The CFRP prepreg sheets were cut into the appropriate size and fiber orientation. The sheets were placed on the vacuum molding board with plain woven fabric CFRP plate to reduce the thermal mismatch between the prepreg and the molding board. CFRP laminates were made using hand lay-up and vacuum bagging technique (no bleeder). Fiber orientation of the hybrid CFRP were set to $[(0_{(IM600)})_2/(0_{(K13D)})_2]_S$, $[(0_{(IM600)})_4/(0_{(K13D)})]_S$, and $[(0_{(IM600)})/(0_{(K13D)})_4]_S$. The fiber volume fractions of the hybrid CFRP were 55.7 vol% (IM600: 29.3 vol%, K13D: 26.4 vol%) for $[(0_{(IM600)})_2/(0_{(K13D)})_2]_S$, 56.3 vol% (IM600: 45.9 vol%, K13D: 10.4 vol%) for $[(0_{(IM600)})_4/(0_{(K13D)})]_S$ and 55.0 vol% for

$[(0_{(IM600)})/(0_{(K13D)})_4]_S$. The prepreg sheets were pressed in 294 kPa and cured in 180 °C for 4 h (heating rate was 1 °C/min) by an autoclave (Ashida Mfg. Co., Ltd., ACA Series) in the laboratory.

The CFRP laminates were cut into rectangular straight side tensile test specimens with dimensions of 200 mm in length (gauge length, L of 100 mm) and 10 mm in width. The fiber axis in the specimen was oriented in line with the length of the tensile test specimen (0° direction specimen). To remove the effect of stress concentrations caused by surface roughness from the edges, the edges of tensile test specimen were polished to remove the scratches. Thinner plain woven fabric glass fiber reinforced plastics (50 mm in length, 10mm in width and 1 mm in thickness) tapered tabs were affixed to the tensile test specimen to minimize damage from the grips on the tensile testing machine.

2.3 Observation

The hybrid CFRP morphologies were observed using a digital microscope (Keyence, VHX-1000/VH-Z100).

2.4 Tensile test

Tensile tests of CFRP specimens were performed using a universal testing machine (Shimadzu, Autograph AG-series) with a load cell of 100 kN. The crosshead speed of 5.0 mm/min was applied. All tests were conducted under the laboratory environment at room temperature (at 23 ± 3 °C and 50 ± 5 % relative humidity). Strain gages were used to measure longitudinal strains. The tensile modulus is calculated using a least square method for the straight line section of stress-strain curve.

3 Results

3.1 Morphologies

Fig. 1 shows the digital microscope images of through-thickness-edge-sectional view morphology for the hybrid CFRP laminates. For the hybrid CFRP laminates, the each layer was clear observed, although, the each layer for the K13D CFRP laminate was obscured. It was found that the each carbon fiber aligned and there were no visible voids in the hybrid CFRP laminate in the through-thickness-sectional view.

(a) $[(0_{(IM600)})_2/(0_{(K13D)})_2]_S$

(b) $[(0_{(IM600)})_4/(0_{(K13D)})]_S$

(c) $[(0_{(IM600)})/(0_{(K13D)})_4]_S$

Fig. 1. Digital microscope images of through-thickness-edge-sectional view for the hybrid CFRP laminates.

3.2 Stress-strain relations and tensile properties

Fig. 2 shows typical tensile stress-strain (σ - ϵ) curve for the hybrid CFRP specimen. For the individual CFRP with 0° direction specimens, the stress applied to the specimen was almost linearly proportional to the strain until failure. However, the tensile stress-strain curves of all hybrid CFRP specimens show complicated shape (jagged trace). By the high modulus K13D CFRP layers, the hybrid CFRP specimen shows the intermediate modulus in the initial stage of loading (this modulus was defined as tensile modulus, E_C).

Fig. 2. Typical tensile stress-strain curves for the hybrid CFRP specimens.

Subsequently, when the K13D CFRP layers begin to fail (this strength and strain were defined as initial fracture strength, σ_{Ci} , and initial failure strain, ϵ_{Ci}), the high strength IM600 CFRP layers would hold the load (this modulus was defined as secondary tensile modulus, E_C^*). The holding stress level is different among each hybrid CFRP specimens and these stresses were defined as holding stress, σ_{Ch} . Finally, the load reached its maximum and fracture of the hybrid CFRP specimen occurred (this strength and strain were defined as tensile strength, σ_{Cf} , and failure strain, ϵ_{Cf}). The average tensile modulus (E_C), tensile strength (σ_{Cf}), failure strain (ϵ_{Cf}), secondary tensile modulus (E_C^*), initial fracture strength (σ_{Ci}), initial failure strain (ϵ_{Ci}) and holding stress (σ_{Ch}) were shown in Table 2 [16].

The initial failure strain of all hybrid CFRP specimens was higher than that of K13D CFRP specimen (8~34 %, enhancement was related to the number of IM600 layers) and the final failure strain of all hybrid CFRP specimen was almost similar to that of IM600 CFRP specimen (2~3 %).

3.3 Failure mode

Fig. 3 shows the fracture features of hybrid CFRP specimen. Splitting fractures were observed in CFRP specimen.

(a) $[(0_{(IM600)})_2/(0_{(K13D)})_2]_S$

(b) $[(0_{(IM600)})_4/(0_{(K13D)})]_S$

(c) $[(0_{(IM600)})/(0_{(K13D)})_4]_S$

Fig. 3. Fracture features of hybrid CFRP laminates.

The failure mode of the $[(0_{(IM600)})/(0_{(K13D)})]_{2S}$ hybrid CFRP specimen was examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) in the previous investigation [16]. As the results, the principal transverse crack related to fibers fracture ran across the whole width and thickness of the K13D CFRP layers. The delamination crack was produced at the intersection of the transverse crack and propagated to the length direction near the interface between the K13D CFRP layers and the IM600 CFRP layers. In this study, the fractures of all hybrid CFRP specimens were also observed the K13D CFRP layers and the failure mode of the hybrid CFRP specimens were almost similar to that of the $[(0_{(IM600)})/(0_{(K13D)})]_{2S}$ hybrid CFRP specimen.

4 Discussions

4.1 Tensile modulus

The tensile modulus and secondary tensile modulus of the hybrid CFRP specimen were calculated using a simple rule of mixtures.

$$E_{C(Hybrid)} = E_{C(IM600)}V_{IM600} + E_{C(K13D)}V_{K13D} \quad (1)$$

(for tensile modulus)

$$E_{C(Hybrid)}^* = E_{C(IM600)}^*V_{IM600} \quad (2)$$

(for secondary modulus)

where $E_{C(IM600)}$, $E_{C(K13D)}$, V_{IM600} and V_{K13D} are the tensile modulus and volume fraction of the IM600 CFRP and K13D CFRP. The estimated tensile modulus, E_C and secondary tensile modulus, E_C^* of the $[(0_{(IM600)})_2/(0_{(K13D)})_2]_S$ hybrid CFRP specimens were 317 and 81 GPa. The estimated E_C and E_C^* of the other hybrid CFRP specimens were 220 and 128 for $[(0_{(IM600)})_4/(0_{(K13D)})]_S$, and 418 and 33 GPa for $[(0_{(IM600)})/(0_{(K13D)})_4]_S$. The experimental results were found to be in agreement with the rule of mixtures prediction. Similar results of hybrid composites were observed in some literatures [17-19].

4.2 Tensile strength and failure strain

The tensile strength and initial fracture strength of the hybrid CFRP specimen were also calculated using the rule of mixtures.

$$\sigma_{C_i(Hybrid)} = \sigma_{C_f(K13D)} V_{K13D} + \varepsilon_{C_f(K13D)} E_{C(IM600)} V_{IM600} \quad (3)$$

(for initial fracture strength)

$$\sigma_{C_f(Hybrid)} = \sigma_{C_f(IM600)} V_{IM600} \quad (4)$$

(for tensile strength)

where $\sigma_{C_f(IM600)}$, $\sigma_{C_f(K13D)}$ and $\varepsilon_{C_f(K13D)}$ are the tensile strength and failure strain of the IM600 CFRP and K13D CFRP specimens. The estimated tensile strength, σ_{C_f} and initial fracture strength, σ_{C_i} of the $[(O_{(IM600)})_2/(O_{(K13D)})_2]_S$ hybrid CFRP specimens were 1.402 and 1.072 GPa. The differences between the calculated and experimental results for tensile strength and initial fracture strength were 7 and 27 %. The estimated σ_{C_f} and σ_{C_i} of the other hybrid CFRP specimens were 2.201 and 0.749 GPa for $[(O_{(IM600)})_4/(O_{(K13D)})_2]_S$, and 0.572 and 1.407 GPa for $[(O_{(IM600)})/(O_{(K13D)})_4]_S$. The differences between the calculated and experimental results for tensile strength and initial fracture strength were 3 and 33 % for $[(O_{(IM600)})_4/(O_{(K13D)})]_S$, and 1 and 2 % for $[(O_{(IM600)})/(O_{(K13D)})_4]_S$. The experimental result of tensile strength was found to be in agreement with the rule of mixtures prediction. The final failure strain, ε_{C_f} is also almost similar to that for the IM600 CFRP specimens. However, a large difference was

observed in the initial fracture strength for $[(O_{(IM600)})_2/(O_{(K13D)})_2]_S$ and $[(O_{(IM600)})_4/(O_{(K13D)})]_S$. The initial failure strain, ε_{C_i} for $[(O_{(IM600)})_2/(O_{(K13D)})_2]_S$ and $[(O_{(IM600)})_4/(O_{(K13D)})]_S$ is also higher than that for the K13D CFRP specimens. Similar results of hybrid composites in which a phenomenon termed “hybrid effect” were also observed in some literatures [9,17-21].

Bunsell *et al* [2] observed the similar enhancement of the initial failure strain in carbon/glass hybrid composite and reported that this effect was attributed to the residual compressive strain between the carbon and the glass plies during curing. In this study, the coefficient of thermal expansion of the IM600 ($\alpha_{C(IM600)}$) and the K13D CFRP specimens ($\alpha_{C(K13D)}$) was about -0.1 and -1.3×10^{-6} ($^{\circ}C$), respectively. The residual compressive strain, $\Delta\varepsilon_{C(K13D)}$ was calculated using the following equation.

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{C(K13D)} = (\alpha_{C(Hybrid)} - \alpha_{C(K13D)}) \Delta T \quad (5)$$

where ΔT is temperature difference and $\Delta T = 157$ $^{\circ}C$ ($= 180 - 23$ $^{\circ}C$). $\alpha_{C(Hybrid)}$ is the estimated coefficient of thermal expansion of the hybrid CFRP specimen and is given by

Table 2. Tensile properties of the hybrid CFRP specimens.

	Tensile modulus E_C (GPa)	Initial fracture strength σ_{C_i} (GPa)	Initial failure strain ε_{C_i} (%)	Secondary tensile modulus E_C^* (GPa)	Tensile strength σ_{C_f} (GPa)	Failure strain ε_{C_f} (%)	Holding stress σ_{Ch} (GPa)
$[(O_{(IM600)})_2/(O_{(K13D)})_2]_S$	314 ± 5	1.361 ± 0.026	0.440 ± 0.011	80 ± 3	1.496 ± 0.050	1.730 ± 0.035	0.628 ± 0.012
$[(O_{(IM600)})_4/(O_{(K13D)})]_S$	206 ± 3	0.997 ± 0.075	0.461 ± 0.020	136 ± 2	2.264 ± 0.053	1.718 ± 0.021	0.705 ± 0.016
$[(O_{(IM600)})/(O_{(K13D)})_4]_S$	411 ± 8	1.432 ± 0.153	0.371 ± 0.032	30 ± 3	0.565 ± 0.072	1.713 ± 0.008	0.356 ± 0.042
IM600 * (QC133-149A)	158 ± 3	-	-	-	2.718 ± 0.127	1.675 ± 0.059	-
K13D * (HYEJ16M95DHX1)	487 ± 7	-	-	-	1.638 ± 0.119	0.343 ± 0.031	-

* from previous investigation [16].

$$\alpha_{C(Hybrid)} = \frac{\alpha_{C(IM600)} E_{C(IM600)} V_{IM600}}{E_{C(IM600)} V_{IM600} + E_{C(K13D)} V_{K13D}} + \frac{\alpha_{C(K13D)} E_{C(K13D)} V_{K13D}}{E_{C(IM600)} V_{IM600} + E_{C(K13D)} V_{K13D}} \quad (6)$$

The residual compressive strain of $[(0_{(IM600)})_2/(0_{(K13D)})_2]_S$, $[(0_{(IM600)})_4/(0_{(K13D)})_4]_S$, and $[(0_{(IM600)})/(0_{(K13D)})_4]_S$ hybrid CFRP was calculated to be 0.011, 0.010, and 0.006 %, respectively. The residual compressive strain slightly affects the increasing of initial failure strain of the hybrid CFRP specimen. This is not however sufficient to explain the whole of the enhancement.

Zweben [22] estimated the strength of hybrid composites from a statistical point of view and statistical works on the strength of hybrid composites have been reported [23-28]. *Aveston et al* [29] suggested that the enhancement of the initial failure strain in hybrid composites might be worthwhile to consider the problem from a synergistic strengthening of more brittle fiber point of view on a fracture energy basis. This approach was found to provide an explanation for the higher failure strains of ceramics matrix composites [30,31]. These (*Zweben* and *Aveston's*) estimations are slight close to the experimental result.

There is a relationship between the ductility layers ratio and the hybrid effect. For the hybrid composites, the fracture of the low elongation K13D CFRP layers is retarded by the greater ductility of the high elongation IM600 CFRP layers.

4.3 Tensile properties and fracture behavior

The fracture behaviors of the hybrid composites were summarized as follow; the stress applied to the specimens was almost linearly proportional to the strain in the initial stage of loading. For the initial fracture stage, the K13D CFRP layers begin to fail. This principal transverse crack runs across the whole width and thickness of the K13D CFRP layers. A delamination crack is produced at the intersection of the transverse crack however this delamination crack is not extended over the whole length of the specimen. This resulted in a sudden reduction in the observed stress and a slightly increasing in strain.

The delamination crack propagated to the length direction near the interface between the K13D CFRP layers and the IM600 CFRP layers and this resulted in an almost constant stress and a large increasing in strain. Finally the delamination crack extended over the whole length of the specimen, so that the K13D CFRP layers became totally unloaded and final fracture considered of fracture of the IM600 CFRP layers. This resulted in a secondary tensile modulus and failure strain.

Total delamination energy release rate, g^D_T is given by the following equation [32-34].

$$g^D_T = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{d\lambda}{da} \quad (7)$$

where P is the applied load with a specimen width B , λ and a are the compliance related to the load-displacement curve and delamination crack length of the hybrid composite. Rearrangement of the total delamination energy release rate expression (Eq. (7)) gives the following:

$$g^D_T = \frac{\sigma^2 AL}{2B} \frac{dS^D_C}{da} \quad (8)$$

where σ is the applied stress with a specimen area A and a gauge length L (=100 mm), S^D_C is the compliance related to the stress-strain curve and given by,

$$S^D_C = \frac{1}{E^D_C} \quad (9)$$

The tensile modulus of the delamination cracked model hybrid CFRP specimen is also given by the rule of mixtures.

$$E^D_{C(Hybrid)} = \frac{E^*_{C(Hybrid)} \cdot a + E_{C(Hybrid)} \cdot (L-a)}{L} \quad (10)$$

The delamination crack length is given by,

$$a = \frac{(E_{C(Hybrid)}^D - E_{C(Hybrid)}) \cdot L}{E_{C(Hybrid)}^* - E_{C(Hybrid)}} \quad (11)$$

From equation (9), (10) and (11), the total delamination energy release rate is modified

$$g^D_T = \frac{\sigma^2 AL^2}{2B} \times \frac{E_{C(Hybrid)}^* - E_{C(Hybrid)}}{((E_{C(Hybrid)}^* - E_{C(Hybrid)}) \cdot a + E_{C(Hybrid)} \cdot L)^2} \quad (12)$$

In a previous investigation [16], delamination-cracked model [(0_(IM600))/(0_(K13D))]_{2S} hybrid CFRP specimen were fabricated using the hand lay-up, vacuum bagging (no bleeder), and autoclave curing to examine the tensile properties and delamination crack growth in the hybrid CFRP. A principal transverse crack was introduced at the center of all K13D CFRP layers. Delamination cracks were produced and controlled using release films. Therefore, for each type of delamination-cracked model hybrid CFRP specimens, the stress applied to the specimens was approximately linearly proportional to the strain during the initial stage of loading. The tensile modulus, E_C^D , of these specimens decreased with increasing delamination crack length, a . Then, a large increase in strain was observed at an approximately constant stress. Finally, the stress-strain curves of delamination-cracked model hybrid CFRP specimens show secondary tensile modulus, and the specimens failed at a similar strain. In addition, total delamination-energy-release rates were calculated using the same procedure, and the initial total delamination-energy-release rates for short delamination crack lengths ($a \leq 20$ mm) were similar (737 ± 22 J/m²).

The initial total delamination energy release rate could be estimated using the holding stress, σ_{Ch} at delamination crack length, $a = 0$. The initial total delamination energy release rates of the [(0_(IM600))₂/(0_(K13D))₂]_S, [(0_(IM600))₄/(0_(K13D))_S], and [(0_(IM600))/(0_(K13D))₄]_S hybrid CFRP specimens were

calculated to be 509 ± 20 , 665 ± 29 and 191 ± 43 and J/m², respectively.

Fig. 4 shows the relation between the total delamination energy-release rate of hybrid CFRP and the tensile modulus. The total delamination-energy-release rate increased with the decreasing tensile modulus of hybrid CFRP, and there is a linear relation between the total delamination-energy-release rate in hybrid CFRP and the tensile modulus of hybrid CFRP.

Fig. 4. Relation between the delamination-energy-release rate of hybrid CFRP and the tensile modulus of hybrid CFRP.

The difference between the total delamination-energy-release rate of hybrid CFRP and the tensile modulus of hybrid CFRP is possibly attributed to mechanisms that contribute to the hybrid ratios (IM600 CFRP layer/K13D CFRP layer). The loading mode of delaminated hybrid CFRP is the mixed mode. The component of mode II was affected by the delamination-energy-release rate of the hybrid CFRP. Moreover, fiber bridging occurred in hybrid CFRP. This mechanism was also affected by delamination-energy-release rate of hybrid CFRP. It is important to consider materials' combinations (i.e., different fibers and base resins) and stacking sequence in hybrid CFRP. In this study, the materials' combination in hybrid CFRP were the same, and delamination-energy-release rates were calculated using the average delamination crack length for each layer (the number of delaminations

was not considered). When the stacking sequence of the hybrid CFRP was changed from $[(O_{(IM600)})_2/(O_{(K13D)})_2]_S$ to $[(O_{(IM600)})/(O_{(K13D)})]_{2S}$, the number of delaminations increased, and a different total delamination-energy-release rate was possibly observed (509 ± 20 and 737 ± 22 J/m²). The fiber/matrix interface adhesion of hybrid CFRP, which is related to the combination of materials, is also important. The weak bonds between the fibers and matrix might cause an interfacial fracture without enhancing the delamination-energy-release-rate.

5 Concluding remarks

The tensile stress-strain curves of all hybrid CFRP specimens show complicated shape (jagged trace). By the high modulus carbon fiber (K13D), the hybrid CFRP specimens show the intermediate modulus in the initial stage of loading. Subsequently, when the high modulus carbon fibers (K13D) begin to fail, the high strength carbon fibers (IM600) would hold the load (strength) and the CFRP specimens continue to endure high load without instantaneous failure.

The initial failure strain in hybrid CFRP was higher than that in K13D CFRP; the final failure strain in hybrid CFRP was similar to that of IM600 CFRP. For hybrid CFRP, the total delamination-energy-release rate estimated from the compliance method using holding stress that increased with decreasing tensile modulus of hybrid CFRP. In addition, there is a linear relation between the total delamination-energy-release rate of hybrid CFRP and the tensile modulus of hybrid CFRP. The stress after the initial failure in hybrid CFRP improved by adding the greater ductility of the high elongation IM600 CFRP layers and correlated with the tensile modulus of the hybrid CFRP.

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References

- [1] E. Fitzer "PAN-based carbon fibers". *Carbon*, Vol. 27, No. 5, pp 621-645, 1989.
- [2] A.R. Bunsell and B. Harris "Hybrid carbon and glass fibre composites". *Composites*, Vol. 5, No. 4, pp 157-164, 1974.
- [3] J. Summerscales and D. Short "Carbon fibre and glass fibre hybrid reinforced plastics". *Composites*, Vol. 9, No. 3, pp 157-166, 1978.
- [4] T. Hayashi, K. Koyama, A. Yamazaki and M. Kihira "Development of new material properties by hybrid composition (2nd Report)". *Fukugo Zairyo (composite materials)*, Vol. 1, pp 21-25, 1972.
- [5] D. Short and J. Summerscales "Hybrids-a review Part 1 Techniques, design and construction". *Composites*, Vol. 10, No. 4, pp 215-221, 1979.
- [6] D. Short and J. Summerscales "Hybrids-a review Part 2 Physical properties". *Composites*, Vol. 11, No. 1, pp 33-38, 1980.
- [7] K.M. Hardaker and M.O.W. Richardson "Trends in hybrid composite technology". *Polymer-Plastics Technology and Engineering*, Vol. 15, No. 2, pp 169-182, 1980.
- [8] T.W. Cho and A. Kelly "Mechanical properties of composites". *Annual Review of Materials Science*, Vol. 10, pp 229-259, 1980.
- [9] P.W. Manders and M.G. Bader "The strength of hybrid glass/carbon fibre composites Part 1 Failure strain enhancement and failure mode". *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 16, No. 8, pp 2233-2245, 1981.
- [10] P. Morgan "*Carbon fibers and their composites*". Taylor, pp 791-859, 2005.
- [11] Y. Huang and R.J. Young "Effect of fibre microstructure upon the modulus of PAN- and pitch-based carbon fibres". *Carbon*, Vol. 33, No. 2, pp 97-107, 1995.
- [12] M.C. Paiva, C.A. Bernardo and M. Nardin "Mechanical, surface and interfacial characterisation of pitch and PAN-based carbon fibres". *Carbon*, Vol. 38, No. 9, pp 1323-1337, 2000.
- [13] K. Naito, Y. Tanaka, J.M. Yang and Y. Kagawa "Tensile Properties of Ultrahigh Strength PAN-based, Ultrahigh Modulus Pitch-based and High Ductility Pitch-based Carbon Fibers". *Carbon*, Vol. 46, No. 2, pp 189-195, 2008.
- [14] K. Naito, Y. Tanaka, J.M. Yang and Y. Kagawa "Flexural Properties of PAN- and Pitch-based Carbon Fibers". *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 92, No. 1, pp 186-192, 2009.
- [15] K. Naito, J.M. Yang, Y. Tanaka and Y. Kagawa "The effect of gauge length on tensile strength and Weibull modulus of polyacrylonitrile (PAN)- and pitch-based

- carbon fibers". *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 47, No. 2, pp 632-642, 2012.
- [16] K. Naito, J.M. Yang and Y. Kagawa "Tensile properties of high strength polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based and high modulus pitch-based hybrid carbon fibers-reinforced epoxy matrix composite". *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 47, No. 6, pp 2743-2751, 2012.
- [17] G. Marom, S. Fischer, F.R. Tuler and H.D. Wagner "Hybrid effects in composites: Conditions for positive or negative effects versus rule-of-mixtures behavior". *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 13, No. 7, pp 1419-1426, 1978.
- [18] M.M. Stevanovic and T.B. Stecenko "Mechanical behaviour of carbon and glass hybrid fibre reinforced polyester composites". *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 27, No. 4, pp 941-946, 1992.
- [19] L. Yao, W.B. Li, N. Wang, W. Li, X. Guo and Y.P. Qiu "Tensile, impact and dielectric properties of three dimensional orthogonal aramid/glass fiber hybrid composites". *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 42, No. 16, pp 6494-6500, 2007.
- [20] G. Kretsis "A review of the tensile, compressive, flexural and shear properties of hybrid fiber-reinforced plastics". *Composites*, Vol. 18, No. 1, pp 13-23, 1987.
- [21] Y.J. You, Y.H. Park, H.Y. Kim and J.S. Park "Hybrid effect on tensile properties of FRP rods with various material compositions". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 80, No. 1, pp 117-122, 2007.
- [22] C. Zweben C "Tensile strength of hybrid composites". *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 12, No. 7, pp 1325-1337, 1977.
- [23] P.W. Manders and M.G. Bader "The strength of hybrid glass/carbon fibre composites Part 2 A statistical model". *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 16, No. 8, pp 2246-2256, 1981.
- [24] H. Fukunaga, T.W. Chou and H. Fukuda "Probabilistic strength analyses of interlaminated hybrid composites". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 35, No. 4, pp 331-345, 1989.
- [25] Y.P. Qiu and P. Schwartz "Micromechanical behavior of Kevlar-149/S-glass hybrid seven-fiber microcomposites: I. Tensile strength of the hybrid composite". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 47, No. 3, pp 289-301, 1993.
- [26] K.D. Jones and A.T. Dibenedetto "Fiber fracture in hybrid composite systems". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 51, No. 1, pp 53-62, 1994.
- [27] H. Fukuda "An advanced theory of the strength of hybrid composites". *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 19, No. 3, pp 974-982, 1984.
- [28] J.M. Hedgepeth "Stress concentrations in filamentary structures". *NASA TN D-882*, 1961.
- [29] J. Aveston and J.M. Sillwood "Synergistic fibre strengthening in hybrid composites". *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 11, No. 10, pp 974-982, 1976.
- [30] B. Budiansky, J.W. Hutchinson and A.G. Evans "Matrix fracture in fiber-reinforced ceramics". *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, Vol. 34, No. 2, pp 167-189, 1986.
- [31] V.I. Kazmin, S.T. Mileiko and V.V. Tvardovsky "Strength of ceramic matrix-metal fibre composites". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 38, No. 1, pp 69-84, 1990.
- [32] G.R. Irwin "Analysis of stresses and strains near the end of a crack traversing a plate". *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 24, pp 361-364, 1957.
- [33] M.L. Benzeggagh, X.J. Gong, A. Laksimi and J.M. Roelandt "On the Mode I delamination test and the importance of laminate lay-ups". *Polymer Engineering & Science*, Vol. 31, No. 17, pp 1286-1292, 1991.
- [34] S.F. Hwang and B.C. Shen "Opening-mode interlaminar fracture toughness of interply hybrid composite materials". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 59, No. 12, pp 1861-1869, 1999.